

Information Needs and Seeking Behaviour of Pregnant Teenage Girls in Yenagoa Metropolis, Bayelsa State

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Abstract

This paper investigated the information needs and information-seeking behaviour of pregnant teenage girls in Yenagoa Metropolis, Bayelsa State. Three (3) objectives were formulated to guide the study, namely to identify the types of information needed, information-seeking behaviour, and the challenges encountered in seeking information by pregnant teenage girls in Yenagoa Metropolis, Bayelsa State. The study population was 570, as reported by the Social Welfare Office of Yenagoa Local Government Area. A purposive sampling technique was adopted to arrive at a sample size of 57 pregnant teenage girls, using 10% of the total population. A questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection; the data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages. One of the findings revealed that pregnant teenage girls in the study area said they needed information on contraceptives and sex education. The paper recommended that governments at all levels should establish libraries and information centres in churches, mosques, kings' palaces, and community town halls to provide information resources on teenage pregnancies.

Keywords: Information, Information Needs, Information Seeking Behaviour, Teenage Pregnancy

Introduction

Information is regarded as an important resource that contributes immensely to a nation's development. Ideally, information leads to knowledge, and a knowledgeable community is also an informed one. This signifies that a community cannot develop without knowledge, and it can only become knowledgeable if it recognises and uses information as a tool for development (Kamba, 2009). Access to the right information by rural communities can help them acquire the skills, knowledge and confidence to participate fully in community affairs. Moore (2007) stated that "Information is a key contributor to the development of individuals and communities. People need information to develop their potential through education and training, to succeed in business, to enrich their cultural experience, and to take control of their daily lives." According to Ozioko (2007), an information need is an imbalance between what a person knows and what they are supposed to know. In other words, there is a gap between the present situation and the more desirable one. This means the person is faced with a need that must be addressed by asking questions, generating ideas, or obtaining resources. Information-seeking behaviour has been defined by Wilson as 'the totality of human behaviour in relation to sources and channels of information, including both active and passive information-seeking and information use' (Wilson, 2016). People from different

walks of life have a need for information because, as the population grows and society becomes more complex, the production and perceived need for information also expand.

Teenage pregnancy is one of the most common problems among adolescents worldwide. Teenage pregnancy is defined as a teenage or underage girl (usually within the ages of 13-19) becoming pregnant. The term in everyday speech usually refers to women who have not reached legal adulthood, which varies across the world, who become pregnant. In the same vein, a teenage pregnancy is formally defined as a pregnancy in a young woman who has not reached her 20th birthday when the pregnancy ends, regardless of whether the woman is married or is legally an adult age 14 to 21, depending on the country (Wikipedia, 2010).

Before this period in Yenagoa, teenage pregnancies were the norm. When a young girl became sexually mature, she was married off and soon accomplished that for which she is biologically designed, giving birth to the next generation. Each child born to a young girl is normally considered a blessing. The situation is different in Yenagoa now; girls are expected to be educated and, for many, to have secure employment before they bear children. Education is considered to be a necessity for living in a complex, information-rich society, and young women today are involved in the workforce at about the same rate as young men. Teenage pregnancies are considered not a blessing but a curse. This is so because most of the children of these pregnancies will grow up fatherless and at high risk themselves of various social and behavioural problems, and the education and work lives of their mothers will be seriously impaired.

In Yenagoa, four in ten girls become pregnant at least once before reaching the age of twenty, with many babies born and children now entering their teenage years; the total number of teenage pregnancies is expected to increase significantly over the next decade.

The most alarming trend associated with teenage pregnancy concerns the decline of early marriage, in that in the 20th century to the early 1990s, early marriage was practised, that is, marriage at younger ages and more restricted sexuality. Today, some teenage pregnancies and teen births are to unmarried girls. These girls lack the maturity, skills, and assistance necessary for good parenting. Teenagers are having more sex, at earlier ages and without the use of contraceptives. Guttmacher Institute (2004) revealed that 60 per cent of girls have their first sexual intercourse before their 13th birthday. Also, Banerjee, Pandey, Dutt, Sengupta, Mondal, and Deb (2009) asserted that early dating of boys and girls from age 12 is a contributing factor to teenage pregnancy since they indulge in sexual activities. Similarly, Miller (2006) posited that girls are having sex at early ages between 10 and 13 years. Lack of parental guidance is another cause of teenage pregnancy in that most people discourage their children from talking about sex. In some cases, they provide false information regarding sex and discourage their children from participating in any informative discussion about sex (Colin, 2003).

Stanley and Swierzeski (2011) opined that teenage pregnancy is a result of poverty. Also, Popenoe (1998) revealed that teenagers who get pregnant are from low socio-economic status parents. Guttmacher Institute (2005) posited that economics may also be responsible for teenagers' childbearing, with childbearing heavily concentrated among poor and low-income teenagers, and that while low-income youths may not intend to have a baby, they may not be sufficiently motivated to avoid pregnancy. Teenage girls who belong to poor families are more likely to get pregnant. Regardless of the situation, pregnant teenage girls constantly seek different types of information for effective decision-making. The study is geared towards assessing the information needs and seeking behaviour of pregnant teenage girls in Yenagoa Metropolis, Bayelsa State.

Statement of the Problem

Every year, an estimated 21 million girls aged 15–19 in developing regions become pregnant, and approximately 12 million give birth (Darroch, 2016). At least 777,000 births occur to adolescent girls younger than 15 in developing countries (UNFPA, 2015). Early pregnancies among adolescents have major health consequences for adolescent mothers and their babies. Pregnancy and childbirth complications are the leading cause of death among girls aged 15–19 globally, with low- and middle-income countries accounting for 99% of global maternal deaths among women. Unmitigated teenage pregnancy and school dropout have enormous cost implications for society. Morbidity and health and social problems associated with teenage pregnancy need not be overemphasised. Teenage pregnancy has medical, psychological and social implications and can be for teenagers the beginning of social deviance. In Nigeria, little or no studies have been conducted on teenage pregnancy. Despite education being a human right, girls in Bayelsa state continue to suffer the indignity of school interruption when they become pregnant (Muganda-Onyando & Omondi, 2008), and most never return to complete their education regardless of the re-entry policy (Omwancha, 2012). This brings to the fore the need to rely exclusively on re-entry; hence the need to identify the information needs, information-seeking behaviour, problems associated with seeking information, and strategies adopted to address these problems by pregnant teenage girls in Yenagoa LGA of Bayelsa State.

Objectives

The main objective of the study is to investigate the information needs and information-seeking behaviour of pregnant teenage girls in Yenagoa LGA of Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study will:

1. Identify information needs of pregnant teenage girls in Yenagoa LGA of Bayelsa state.
2. Determine the information-seeking behaviour of pregnant teenage girls in Yenagoa LGA of Bayelsa state.
3. Find out the problems associated with seeking information by pregnant teenage girls in Yenagoa LGA of Bayelsa state.

Literature Review

Information

Information means many things to many people, depending on the context. Scientifically, information is processed data. Information can also be loosely defined as that which aids decision-making. Information, though abstract, could also be visualised as a commodity that can be bought or sold. Kilic (2010) added that: “any potentially useful fact, quantity or value that can be expressed uniquely with exactness. Information is whatever is capable of causing a human mind to change its opinion about the current state of the real world.

Buckland (1991) analysed the dictionary meanings in the Oxford English Dictionary and identified three distinct meanings as follows. Information as a process: When someone is informed, what they know changes. In this sense, “Information is the act of information communication of the knowledge or news of some fact or occurrence; the act of telling a fact or being told of something.” Information as knowledge: Information is also used to denote what is perceived in information as a process; the knowledge communicated concerning some particular fact, subject or event; that of which one is apprised or told, intelligence, news. Moore (2007) viewed information as “data that has been put into a meaningful and

useful context and communicated to a recipient who uses it to make a decision” Daniel (2009) used a broader approach in his definition of information, viewing it as “knowledge used in its generic sense irrespective of the source, format, mode or transfer medium”. In his rather simplistic attempt to define information, Norton (2019) categorised it as ranging “from articles and technical publications to verbal reports of informal meetings and from news items in daily or trade newspapers to patent specifications”.

There is no gainsaying that the present world order is strictly ruled by the power of information rather than that of money. Unlike several decades ago, the world today has come to a full realisation of the fact that information “is the prime commodity of the present age” (Olarenwaju & Falola, 2015). This is especially true of the advanced countries of the world, where this has long been established as a reality. As for the majority of developing countries, which are yet to reach such an advanced stage of realising their significance, they are fast coming to terms with the inescapable reality of this.

Information Need

An individual’s or a group’s desire to locate and obtain information to satisfy a conscious or unconscious need. Information need refers to each individual user's information needs. It is understood as an evolving, vague awareness of a gap, culminating in the location of information that contributes to understanding and meaning (Doraswamy, 2017). Information behaviour is the totality of human behaviour in relation to sources and channels of information. Information-seeking behaviour is the purposive search for information to achieve a goal. Information search behaviour is the micro-level behaviour employed by the information seeker when interacting with information systems of all kinds. Information use behaviour comprises the mental and physical acts involved in incorporating information into a person’s existing knowledge base.

Information Seeking Behaviour

Information-seeking behaviour is a process in which people search for information and use it to complete their assigned tasks. Information is essentially structured or processed data. People need information in all walks of life. According to Sultana, Ayesha (2016), the term information-seeking behaviour involves a set of actions, including identifying information needs, seeking information, evaluating and selecting it, and finally using it. Information-seeking is the process humans engage in to change their state of knowledge. It is a high-level cognitive process that is part of learning or problem-solving. Seeking information implies the need to change the state of one’s knowledge. Because of new information formats, information sources, and information tools, users are expected to acquire new knowledge and skills in information searching (Kaushik, 2011). According to Wilson (2000), information-seeking behaviour is the purposive seeking of information to satisfy a goal. According to King, information-seeking behaviour is “a manner in which a user conducts himself in relation to a given information environment”. According to Kritels, “it refers to any activity of an individual that is undertaken to identify a message that satisfies a perceived need”. According to Girija Kumar, information-seeking behaviour is mainly concerned with the need, what kind of information is sought, what, how information is found, evaluated, and used, and how needs can be identified and satisfied.

Pregnant Teenage Girls

Teenage pregnancy, also known as adolescent pregnancy, is a pregnancy in a female under the age of 20, according to the WHO. Pregnancy can occur with sexual intercourse after the start of ovulation, which can be before the first menstrual period (menarche) but usually occurs after the onset of periods. In well-nourished girls, the first period usually occurs around age 12 or 13. Pregnant teenagers face many of the

same pregnancy-related issues as other women. There are additional concerns for those under the age of 15 as they are less likely to be physically developed to sustain a healthy pregnancy or to give birth. For girls aged 15–19, risks are more strongly associated with socioeconomic factors than with the biological effects of age. Risks of low birth weight, premature labour, anaemia, and pre-eclampsia are connected to biological age, as they are observed in teen births even after controlling for other risk factors, such as access to prenatal care. Teenage pregnancies are associated with social issues, including lower educational levels and poverty. In developed countries, teenage pregnancy is usually outside marriage and often carries social stigma. In developing countries, teenage pregnancy often occurs within marriage, and half are planned. However, in these societies, early pregnancy may combine with malnutrition and poor health care to cause medical problems. When used together, educational interventions and access to birth control can reduce unintended teenage pregnancies.

In 2015, about 47 females per 1,000 had children under the age of 20. Rates are higher in Africa and lower in Asia. In the developing world, about 2.5 million females under 16 and 16 million aged 15 to 19 have children each year. Another 3.9 million have abortions. It is more common in rural than in urban areas. Worldwide, pregnancy-related complications are the leading cause of death among females aged 15 to 19. The mother's age is determined by the easily verified date of delivery, not by the estimated date of conception. Consequently, the statistics do not include pregnancies that began at age 19 but ended on or after the woman's 20th birthday. Similarly, statistics on the mother's marital status are determined by whether she is married at the end of the pregnancy, not at the time of conception.

Methodology

This study employs a descriptive research design. According to Kilic (2010), a descriptive survey is ideal for illustrating situations without any manipulation, focusing on collecting and describing existing data and events. This approach is suitable here because the study aims to understand the information needs and seeking behaviour of pregnant teenage girls in Yenagoa LGA, Bayelsa State. The research was conducted in Yenagoa LGA, where the Social Welfare Department of the Bayelsa State Ministry of Justice (2020) estimated approximately 570 cases of teenage pregnancy in the Yenagoa Metropolis, which formed the study's population. Purposive sampling was used to select 57 teenage mothers aged 13-19, representing about 10% of the population, based on Atoyebi (2018), who noted that a 10% sample suffices for populations above 500. Data were collected using a researcher-developed questionnaire divided into four sections, each aligned with a research question. The instrument's face validity was tested by experts in Library and Information Science and Measurement and Evaluation at Niger-Delta University, Amasoma, Bayelsa State. It was then pilot-tested with 8 teenage mothers in Choba, Rivers State. The internal consistency was measured using Cronbach's Alpha, with reliability coefficients of 0.82, 0.87, 0.81, and 0.89 for the four clusters, and an overall reliability of 0.96, indicating high reliability. The questionnaire was administered at antenatal and postnatal centres in Yenagoa Metropolis and collected immediately by the researcher, assisted by three trained research assistants. Data analysis involved descriptive statistics, specifically frequencies and percentages, to address the research questions.

Results

Fifty-seven (57) questionnaires were distributed and retrieved without losing any. This represents 100% response rate. The data analysis reflected the four research questions formulated for the study.

Research Question One

What are the information needs of pregnant teenage girls in Yenagoa LGA of Bayelsa state?

The data used to answer the above stated question are presented in Table 1 below;

Table 1: Information Needs of Pregnant Teenage Girls

S/N	Information needs of pregnant teenage girls	pregnant teenage girls			
		Agree		Disagree	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1	Information on sex education	52	91	4	7
2	Information on Baby care	52	91	5	8
3	Information on school entry requirements	56	98	1	1
4	Information on baby’s health management	54	94	3	6
5	Information on contraceptives	57	100	0	0
6	Information on entrepreneurship	53	92	4	7
7	Information on disease prevention and control	56	98	1	1
8	Information on teenage pregnancy prevention	23	40	34	59
9	Information on teenage pregnancy health risks	31	54	26	45
10	Information on teenage pregnancy symptoms	12	21	45	36

Table 1 above shows the information needs of pregnant teenage girls. Information on contraceptives ranks highest with 100% as opined by pregnant teenage girls in Yenagoa L.G.A Out of the 57, the pregnant teenage girls in the study area overwhelmingly agreed that they need information on sex education, baby care, school entry requirements, baby’s health management, entrepreneurship, disease prevention and control. Only 12 (21%) agreed that they need Information on teenage pregnancy symptoms, constituting the least response. This finding corroborates the thoughts of Kari and Yusuf (2019); that the girl child in Bayelsa state seeks information about food, health, education, business and best agricultural practices. It is mostly about the quest for survival.

Research Question Two

What are the information-seeking behaviours of pregnant teenage girls in Yenagoa LGA of Bayelsa State?

The data for answering the above research question are presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Information-seeking behaviour of pregnant teenage girls

S/N	Information-seeking behaviour of tricycle pregnant teenage girls transport operators	pregnant teenage girls			
		Agree		Disagree	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1	Doctors and Nurses	45	78	12	21
2	Information from radio and television sets	56	98	1	1

3	Information from family members	57	100	0	0
4	Information from government agencies in Pamphlets, posters and banners	45	78	12	21
5	Consulting Newspapers or Magazines	12	21	45	78
6	Information from prenatal health education classes	46	80	11	19
7	Information from the Internet	56	98	1	1
8	Information from social media	56	98	1	1
9	Information from the Library	13	22	44	77

Pregnant teenage girls were asked about their level of agreement on their information-seeking behaviour, with two options: agree and disagree. Table 2 revealed that majority of respondents agreed that they seek information from their family members (100%), radio and television sets (98%), Internet and social media (98%); Pre-Natal health education classes (80%), Library and newspapers got the least response of 22% and 21% respectively this implies that library as an information centre did not serve as an information source to pregnant teenage girls

Research Question Three

What are the problems associated with seeking information by pregnant teenage girls in Yenagoa LGA of Bayelsa State?

The data for answering the above research question are presented in Table 3 below:

Table 3: problems associated with seeking information by pregnant teenage girls

S/N	problems associated with seeking information	pregnant teenage girls			
		Agree		Disagree	
		Freq.	%	Freq.	%
1	Inability to use social media	45	78	12	22
2	High cost of information	2	3	55	97
3	Non-available health information resources	53	92	4	8
4	Level of education	49	85	8	15
5	Lack of library or information centres	57	100	0	0
6	Lack of mobile phones	56	98	1	2
7	Lack of lack of qualified health professionals	57	100	0	0
8	Distance to the source of information	53	92	4	8
9	Lack of awareness of the existence of information	47	82	10	18
10	Insecurity	53	92	4	8

Table 3 revealed the problems associated with seeking information by pregnant teenage girls. Lack of library or information centres (100%); Lack of lack of qualified health professionals (100%); Lack of mobile phones (98%); Non available health information resources (92%); Distance to the source of information (92%); Insecurity (92%); Level of education (85%); were agreed overwhelmingly by the pregnant teenage girls as problems associated with seeking information. High cost of information was not seen as a problem associated with seeking information by the pregnant teenage girls in Yenagoa L.G.A of Bayelsa State

Discussion

The study has undoubtedly established facts regarding the information needs and seeking behaviour of pregnant teenage girls. It has been shown that many pregnant teenage girls need information on contraceptives, which ranked highest at 100%. The pregnant teenage girls in the study area overwhelmingly agreed that they need information on sex education, baby care, school entry requirements, baby's health management, entrepreneurship, disease prevention and control. Only 12 (21%) agreed that they need information on teenage pregnancy symptoms, which constituted the least response. This finding corroborates the views of Kari and Yusuf (2019) that the girl child in Bayelsa State seeks information on food, health, education, business, and best agricultural practices. It is mostly about the quest for survival.

Pregnant teenage girls in the study area reported seeking information from family members, radio and television, the Internet, social media, and antenatal health education classes. Libraries and newspapers received the fewest responses as sources of information. This suggests that the library, as an information centre, did not serve as a source of information for pregnant teenage girls. This finding aligns with those of Patterson (1976), Wilson (1987), and Kalu (2008) on the sources of information and information-seeking behaviour of people in business and other vocations.

Problems associated with seeking information among pregnant teenage girls, as overwhelmingly agreed by them, included a lack of libraries or information centres, a lack of qualified health professionals, insecurity, a lack of mobile phones, low levels of education, and a lack of awareness of the existence of information. This aligns with Afolabi (2003) and Cerevo (2004), who stated that the problems of information seeking have to do with economic, social, environmental, occupational, and infrastructure issues. Also, Okah (2008) agreed that illiteracy is another problem that hinders their understanding of the rules of the road and general traffic regulations.

Conclusion

The importance of information for everyone cannot be overstated. This study examined the information needs and seeking behaviour of pregnant teenage girls in Yenagoa LGA. The findings were both revealing and interesting. They showed that each group in society has their own specific information needs and methods of obtaining that information. Specifically, the study revealed that these pregnant teenage girls require information on contraceptives, sex education, baby care, school admission requirements, baby's health management, entrepreneurship, and disease prevention and control. They rely on family members, radio, television, the Internet, social media, and prenatal health education classes. However, they face challenges in accessing this information, including the absence of libraries or information centres, a shortage of qualified health professionals, insecurity, limited access to mobile phones, varying levels of education, and limited awareness of available information.

Recommendations

The study made some recommendations to deal with the problems the pregnant teenage girls encounter while seeking information.

1. It was discovered that if adult literacy classes are organised for the pregnant teenage girls at designated centres, the problem of illiteracy will be reduced.
2. Furthermore, public libraries should be organising workshops through which the pregnant teenage girls will be educated and given entrepreneurial skills.

3. Poverty has been identified as a major cause of teenage pregnancy, poverty alleviation schemes should be established by the federal, state and local governments to take teenage girls and their parents out of poverty
4. Pregnant teenage girls should be given scholarships to go back to school by oil companies as part of their corporate social responsibility. This will address the problem of school enrolment

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